

SPECTRAL RESPONSES OF HF SIGNALS DURING THE SOLAR ECLIPSE OF APRIL 08, 2024

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During solar eclipses, fluctuations in solar ionizing radiation flux typically occur more rapidly than under normal conditions. Consequently, observations of the ionosphere's response to eclipses provide valuable experimental data on the characteristics of ionospheric processes at various altitudes.

During the total solar eclipse of April 8, 2024, we conducted HF Doppler measurements using signals of the time service station (CHU), as well as dedicated transmission from the Ukrainian Antarctic Akademik Vernadsky station (UAS). These signals we registered at several receive sites: near Fredericton (Canada), in Boston (USA), at the LOFAR PL610 observatory (Borowiec, Poland), in Tromsø (Norway), at the UAS, and onboard the Ukrainian research vessel *Noosfera* (she was near the Antarctic Peninsula during the eclipse). Thus, these HF signal paths were close to or intersected with the trajectory of the lunar full and partial shadow.

Doppler frequency shifts (DFS) variations in the received signals revealed clear responses to the eclipse on the CHU-Fredericton, CHU-Boston, and CHU-PL610 radio paths. On the CHU-Noosfera path, changes in signal characteristics at 14670 kHz were also observed on the day of the eclipse.

To interpret the effects of the eclipse, we calculated the variations in the integrated solar luminance (ISL) along the HF radio paths. This approach had been tested earlier to explain the effects of the solar eclipse of 2008. It was shown that, on medium and long-range radio paths, photochemical processes in the lower ionosphere mainly affect the characteristics of the HF signal. The DFS variations were found to be proportional to the derivative of the ISL at all frequencies. Notably, stronger DFS variations occurred at lower sounding frequencies during the eclipse, suggesting that these variations are driven more by changes in electron density along the radio path than by changes in the HF signal reflection height.

A comparison of the modeling to the April 8, 2024, eclipse observations confirmed earlier results obtained for medium and short radio paths. Therefore, the amplitude of the DFS variations on the CHU-Boston path at the sounding frequency of 3330 kHz was greater than that at 7850 kHz, which confirms the primary role of the changes in electron density along the radio path. The ionospheric response to the eclipse was also observed for the CHU 14670 kHz signal, which was above the maximum usable frequencies for the receive sites in Boston and Fredericton. For this frequency, a significant time shift between the DFS variations and the derivative of the ISL on the straight paths was observed.

We propose hypotheses regarding the possible propagation modes that may explain the observed DFS at this frequency. Raytracing modeling results for the HF signal propagation through the region of totality on single-hop radio links are also presented.